

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and
assessment of plastic pollution

Short report on methods and protocols for the analysis of nano-, micro-, and macroplastic in water samples

EUROqCHARM Short Report

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R	Report	x
DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
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About EUROqCHARM

This report is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic litter globally, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments, and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

In Task 1.2 from WP1 of the EUROqCHARM project, a Systematic Review (SR) was carried out to analyse the matrix- and size- adapted methods reported in the literature for water samples. Methodological steps from sampling to data management were arranged in Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs) and assessed for the Technological Readiness Level (TRL), which may eventually (if not already) be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes.

Optimising the processes involved in plastic monitoring and analysis is of high priority. Therefore, by introducing RAPs into plastics pollution research, the EUROqCHARM project has been providing guidance for the coordination of monitoring activities at the European level, whilst strengthening the generation of sound scientific knowledge and support strategic actions.

The goal of WP1 T1.2 was achieved through addressing plastics in different water matrices and in different size ranges (nano, micro, macroplastics). To do so, we rely on expert opinion and SR data analysis.

Robust and repeatable methods were regularly used in some papers and we accounted them for representative of complete and mature RAPs that have the properties to be recommended for monitoring procedures. In other instances, the technology is not mature yet or, as in the case of air, at pioneering stage of science.

A series of recommendations were extracted after our SR and they refer to monitoring in water but also to the general aspects of environmental plastic science.

This report is not intended to define the best methods and protocols for analysis, which is the objective of other work packages in EUROqCHARM and dedicated Working Groups, but aims to identify the properties of the fundamental steps of the analytical process and the methods and protocols that are more widely used for monitoring as from scientific literature.

We **showcase the potential of integration of TRLs and RAPs as a tool for systematic description** of analytical procedures for plastics in the environment and as a fundamental decision-making support tool. To support monitoring, it is necessary to define recommended approaches, which are reproducible and comparable when applied between national, regional and local. Such methods cannot be recommended if they do not meet the requirements of a certain TRL level.

Acknowledgments

This report was compiled by members of WP1 Task 1.2: Sebastian Primpke, Lisa Rocher (AWI), Amy Lusher (NIVA), Stefano Aliani, Giuseppe Suaria, Andrea Paluselli (CNR-ISMAR).

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List of acronyms

Acronyms	Definition
EU	European Union
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission
ILC	Interlaboratory Comparison exercise
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention
RAPs	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
SR	Systematic Review
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRL	Technological Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WP	Work Package

Acronym	Full name
NIVA	Norsk institutt for vannforskning <i>Norwegian Institute for Water Research</i>
CNR-ISMAR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Scienze Marine <i>National Research Council, Institute of Marine Sciences (Italy)</i>
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz- Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung <i>Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research</i>

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large-scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability, and reliability. The main goal of the first EUROqCHARM Work Package (WP1) was to define matrix- and size- adapted methods which may eventually be incorporated into plastic monitoring programmes. To do so, WP1 used a systematic approach to assess methods employed by the international research community and identify state-of-the art procedures for sample collection, sample preparation and analysis of plastics from environmental samples to define matrix- and size- adapted method. **Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs)** could be extracted for each element in the analytical chain, resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP was further validated in terms of **Technological Readiness Level (TRL)** to decide if further validation is needed.

The workload was thereby divided across four tasks addressing plastics in different size ranges (nano-, micro-, macroplastics) in different matrices (water, soil/sediment, air, biota). The specific objectives of WP1 were to:

- Identify existing methods - including the level of currently applied QA/QC procedures for the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macroplastics in different matrices.
- Evaluate the identified methods for their suitability to be incorporated into monitoring programmes including their advantages and limitations. The most promising methods were suggested for validation and quality control in WP2 or direct implementation into WP3.

Therefore, the **key outputs** of WP1 were to compile existing methods and protocols used to quantify plastics in environmental matrices (using RAPs), evaluate them for further validation (WP2) or direct implementation in monitoring programmes (WP3);

The main actions in WP1 were:

- Systematic literature review;
- Synthesis of existing methods and procedures;
- Compilation of Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAPs);
- Analyses of methods Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT);
- Suggestions for critical revisions of identified monitoring methods.

All these objectives and tasks were attempted for plastic of sizes ranging from macro- to nanoplastics in water, sediment, biota and air, with both marine and terrestrial environments.

In the present report, **the RAPs from plastics in water samples are shortly presented.**

2. Methods

Data analysis was performed after a systematic literature review by the readers of partners AWI, CNR and NIVA (see Aliani et al. 2023 for details of the systematic review and definitions used in this report). All data were collected by the task leader (AWI) and a general quality control/quality assurance performed. It was conducted by the selection of a few investigated references and reconfirmation of the assigned entries. Differences were, if necessary, addressed by a reassessment of provided entries to achieve a consistent dataset.

3. Results

For the water compartment, the target size of plastics and sampling method are inherently linked, whilst the subcompartments play a smaller role in method choice. Overall, the systematic review (SR) returned over 750 publications, of which over 580 were retained after quality control. These references provided information covering multiple litter types and sizes, different sub-compartments, applied different sampling device, sample preparation, analysis techniques or reported in different metric unit(s) and generate as a series of data entries (over 1900 unique entries). For example, if a publication was assessed for micro- litter type, it can yield the number of 1, as it only investigated microplastics, while it may consist of a higher number of unique dataset entries if the publication applied multiple analytical techniques within the study. This allows a very detailed analysis and in the following the term “entry” is used instead of referring to the number of publications. Further, the term Unique Database Entry (UDE) needed to be introduced, if the data was tested if providing multiple entries. Given this, the summary of publications on water can be presented in two ways:

- 1) Investigating by the size of plastics, a total of 703 database entries were obtained, of which 16.9 were for macroplastics, 10.8% for mesoplastics, 70.3% for microplastics, and 2.0% for nanoplastics.
- 2) Investigating by survey design and sampling approach: Many of the investigated studies which targeted a specific sub-compartment (like e.g., sea surface water), often did so by an individual sampling approach (e.g., a net). If a study targeted more than one sub-compartment (e.g., sea surface and water column) the publications often used two different sampling devices (e.g., a net and a pump). This resulted in a total of 812 entries, of which 16.4 % contributed to macro-, 10.3 % to meso-, 71.2 %to micro- and 2.1 % to nano-plastics.

Due to this, only **the identification of RAPs could be performed for macro-, meso- and microplastics**. Limited papers were retrieved on nanoplastics hampering the construction of RAPs for this size class. In this report only RAPs were reported with a TRL > 6 (n>20) or higher.

To address the water publications in the most efficient way, we first present the general trends and survey design irrespective of size category (Section 3.1.1), and sample collection (Section 3.1.2). The remaining analytical elements are presented by size classes of plastics in the subsequent sections: macroplastics (Section 3.1.3.), mesoplastics (Section 3.1.4), microplastics (from Section 3.1.5). Microplastics is further divided into seawater, terrestrial water (incl. freshwater systems) and wastewater to handle data for RAPs.

3.1. RAPs for plastics in water

3.1.1. Survey design and general trends for plastic analysis in water (all size classes)

Some general trends can be seen when addressing the individual size classes in relation to year of publication. The first records of investigations of macroplastic in water obtained by this SR were published in 1992. Publications were sporadic until macroplastic research gained significant focus after 2010. The number of publications for micro- and mesoplastics started to increase from 2013, while the investigation of nanoplastics started around 2017. In all cases the highest numbers of publications were reached in 2020.

On a global scale most studies were performed in Asia and Europe for macro-, meso- and microplastics. These are followed by studies from North America, Africa and South America, while only a limited number of studies were performed in Oceania and Antarctica. For nanoplastics eight publications came from Europe, Asia, North America and South America and six were pure lab studies reflecting the method development focus.

Only 20% of investigated waterbodies were covered by different Regional Sea Conventions, with 8.0% for the Mediterranean, 6.6% for the OSPAR regions, 2.7% for the Baltic Sea (HELCOM), 1.8% for the Arctic and 0.8 % for the Black Sea.

Most of the macro-, meso- and microplastics publications presented results from research projects followed by monitoring and method development. The majority of the nanoplastics publications were mainly focusing on method development. These results highlight the movement of individual research projects towards monitoring activities. To avoid a bias survey design is not discussed further to retain the comparability of the determined RAPs.

3.1.2. Sample collection for plastic analysis in water (all size classes)

The plastic size information would already be sufficient to start a RAP analysis, when introducing a second factor of sampling device, the situation becomes more complicated. Here, similar methods (i.e., different types of net sampling) were collapsed into a generalised method category. From the obtained data it was found that sample collection methods can be used to determine RAPs for the size groups of macro-, meso- and microplastics.

For macro-sized particles, visual surveys and net sampling have a major role ($n > 20$), while aerial surveys and the manual collection of items can only be addressed with a detailed analysis. For micro-sized particles commonly applied sampling strategies had been net-, pump-based- or bucket/grab sampling while nanoplastics cannot be further investigated.

3.1.3. RAPs for macroplastic analysis in water

Sample collection, sample preparation and analytical detection

Macroplastic assessments were dominated by visual surveys and net sampling (> 20 entries each), followed by remote sensing/aerial surveys and manual collection (> 10 entries each).

Where visual observation is represented by a single sampling procedure (see Figure 1), net sampling is a combination of different nets and net sampling strategies. None of the approaches reached the minimum number of ten for a more detailed analysis. This indicates that the exact details of a net are either not considered of importance for macroplastic sampling or the items were by-catch to the original targeted litter type (60% of the entries) and net sampling (see Figure 1) was used as a general term in this short report.

Figure 1 – Reproducible analytical pipeline for the identification of macroplastics using visual surveys and net sampling.

The analysis of macroplastics using **visual surveys** followed a common pathway (Figure 1). Visual surveys applied for sea water (70%) and terrestrial waters (30%) and targeted the water surface. In all cases the analytical approach was object identification which normally follows an existing monitoring guideline (67%) or visual identification (23%).

Net sampling was sampling reporting the presence of macroplastics combined with the data for meso- and microplastics 46% and to a far lesser extent with mesoplastics (8%). Targeted macroplastic net sampling accounts for 46%. While the combined sampling was applied in a nearby equal share, the combination yielded commonly higher share of identification techniques involved. In contrast to visual surveys, net samples often include a sample preparation technique, mainly visual separation (71%) but also sieving (24%) and/or density separation (12%). To identify the plastics, either a hot needle test/melt point assessment, FTIR analysis or another technique was performed. In 18% of the studies no separation was reported. Moreover, only in 8% the sample volume (> 1 m³) was reported.

The **manual collection** of macroplastics (and other litter) from the sea surface by hand/tools or in the water column by divers was reported on a constant and low rate over the last years, mainly investigating surface waters of sea or terrestrial origin. In the most cases the objects were directly sorted and characterised using object or visual identification. In two cases, the polymer type was determined by ATR-FTIR. Most of the publications was either for monitoring or a research project while three of the publications were designed for citizen science. Often own reporting protocols were applied while in one case the OSPAR 100 m beach litter protocol was adapted.

Some interesting alternatives to visual surveys are ones based on **remote sensing or aerial systems** such as planes or drones. At the time of the SR, such systems were mainly tested for surface waters using object identification or hyperspectral imaging techniques.

Plastic quantification and data reporting

Visual surveys primarily use the EU/JRC MSFD protocol (Hanke et al. 2013) for plastic (and other litter items) identification and quantification. Only a low number of studies used either NOAA (Masura et al. 2015) or UNEP (Cheshire et al. 2009) protocols for net sampling and most studies applied own protocols or referred either to other protocols or other publications. The raw data was only reported in 30% of the investigated studies for macroplastics.

3.1.4. RAPs for mesoplastic analysis in water

The analysis of mesoplastics by net sampling is often performed in combination with the analysis of microplastics (53 %) or macro- and microplastics (n = 27%), while a targeted mesoplastics analysis only yields (15%, n<10) subcompartment entries. The combination of macro/meso analysis was applied for 5% of the investigated studies.

An increase was seen regarding identification techniques where the number of targeted mesoplastic entries increased by 22%. When combined with microplastics (82% increase) and in combination with macro-/microplastics (47% increase) an even stronger effect was found.

As the number of the targeted studies is below the threshold, it was concluded that a single RAP for mesoplastics is not available at the time of the EUROqCHARM SR. Due to the high number of studies which combine meso- and microplastics assessment, the RAPs presented from Section 3.1.5 could be used to inform mesoplastic sampling.

3.1.5. RAPs for microplastic analysis in water samples: **General**

Two potential pathways for RAPs were investigated prior to a full dataset analysis. The most reported microplastic sampling techniques were net sampling (45%), grab/bucket sampling (27%) and pump sampling (15%). For 13% of the microplastic entries, sampling techniques were either not reported/not applicable, or denoted as “others”. Similar to the initial data assessment, the sub-compartment was added as a quality control analysis.

The sub-compartments most targeted for microplastics were seawater (39%), terrestrial water (27%) and wastewater (22%). Sub-compartments assigned to “others” include snow/ice, tap or drinking water, or ground water which did not reach the minimum requirements for analysis. Based on these initial results, it was necessary to distinguish between the sub-compartments seawater, terrestrial water and wastewater as starting points for RAPs due to the high number of publications in each sub-compartment.

3.1.6. RAPs for microplastic analysis in water: **Seawater**

Sample collection

Sampling techniques for microplastics in seawater were net (67 %), bucket/grab (17%) and pump sampling (11 %). These techniques were applied with lower detection limits ranging from 1 mm down to <0.1 mm.

Within the investigated studies net samples were mostly reported with minimum sizes of 0.3-1 mm (55 %). On closer inspection, this was due to the application of nets with mesh sizes between 0.3-0.35 mm. Lower mesh sizes were applied to a lesser extent. Further, the reported data showed the performance of a sample splitting within a part of the investigated studies.

In the cases of bucket/grab and pump sampling, most studies reported lower detection limits with minimum sizes <0.1 mm (52% and 54%, respectively). Also here, the reported data showed the performance of sample splitting.

Sample preparation

For seawater, differences in sample preparation were found between net, pump and bucket/grab sampling. Net samples (2 steps or less, 55%) generally underwent less processing steps than samples collected with pump (2 or 3 steps, 50%) or bucket/grab sampling (2 or 3 steps, 56%). For net sampling entries, 27% applied oxidative digestion, whereas it was applied more often for pump and bucket/grab sampling (~40% each). In contrast, visual separation had a far higher share (78%) for net sampling compared to pump and bucket/grab sampling (~60%). This is likely related to the larger minimum size of investigated items for net sampling as many cases applied as first processing step. Filtration was only performed in 41% of the net sampling entries (pump sampling: 87%, bucket/grab: 90%). Sieving and density separation were applied in a minimum of 15% of the investigated studies for each sampling approach, with a higher share for net sampling (>30%).

Analytical detection and plastic quantification

In all sampling approaches, optical microscopy and FTIR were reported (>50%) with the highest application rates while visual/object identification and Raman analysis were applied with a similar share (~10% each). Further, many studies used more than one technique which is reflected in the following percentages and Figure 2.

Remarkably, Raman analysis was often performed in combination with pump samples whilst dye staining was used more often for both pump and bucket/grab sampling (10 – 8%). Also, net and pump sampling had a higher use of unaided visual identification. SEM was applied in only a few reported cases, with the highest share for bucket/grab sampling (8%). Further details are presented in the combined section on analytical detection (Section 3.1.11).

Data reporting

For seawater, the reporting of sample volume was a major issue for net sampling as in 44% the sample volume was not reported, especially in the earlier studies, while the reporting increased within the recent years leading to 49% of the studies reported the sampling of volumes >1 m³. A similar share was applied for pump samples, while 32% of the studies applied a volume between 10L and 1m³. For bucket/grab sampling, sampling volumes did not exceed 1 m³ but in 50% of the studies reached a range between 1 m³ and 10 L, while 43% reported volumes below 10L.

The sample volumes are also reflected in the applied unit for reporting with net sampling and pump sampling report in items/m³ as major unit and with items/L for. Only for net sampling area-based units, with mainly items/km² (19%) and grams/km² (10%) were reported. Especially for net sampling studies reported a high share of other units and multiple units per publication. Among all studies, shapes and colours were reported in 81% and 53% of the cases, respectively. All results are summarised in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Overview of reporting of sample collection, lowest size limit, sample preparation, analytical detection, sample volumes, units, shapes and colours, displayed for net, pump and bucket/grab sampling of seawater.

3.1.7. RAP for microplastic analysis in water: Terrestrial water

Terrestrial waters are defined as water systems in the terrestrial ecosystem, including freshwater rivers, lakes and streams.

Sample collection

Sample collection in terrestrial waters was mainly performed with nets (46%), bucket/grab sampling devices (33%) and pumps (15%). Similar to seawater sampling, net sampling showed a maximum number of publications using reporting a lower size detection limit between 0.3 - 1 mm (41%), while pump as well as bucket/grab samples had their maximum at <0.1 mm (71% and 64%, respectively).

Sample preparation

For terrestrial water, the reporting of size fractions by sample splitting was visible all sampling methods. Terrestrial water sampling is often followed by a series of sample preparation steps independent of the sampling method. While net sampling in seawater had a maximum of one sample preparation step, terrestrial water samples mostly used three or four steps.

The relative share of the type of processing step showed similar trends compared to seawater. As the number of steps increased, the number of density separation and oxidative digestion increased systematically for all approaches. Further, the number of sieving and filtration steps increased for net sampling. In contrast, the share of visual separations steps for net sampling and sieving for pump sampling decreased. This indicates the presence of a more complex sample matrix, requiring organic matter digestion. Further details are presented in the combined section on sample preparation (Section 3.1.10).

Analytical detection and plastic quantification

Most of the studies applied optical microscopy (>75% for all devices) and FTIR based analyses (>50% for all devices). The use of Raman spectroscopy (12% - 37%) and SEM analysis (11 - 31%) was higher than with seawater samples. Other methods included thermoanalytical (11% for net sampling) approaches, fluorescent staining (10 % for bucket/grab and pump sampling) and the testing of the physical properties of particles (up to 7% for net and bucket/grab sampling). Further details are presented in the combined section on analytical detection (Section 3.1.11).

Data reporting

For terrestrial water sampling, the reporting of sample volume was also a major issue for net sampling with a share 29% of not reported of the investigated studies. However, 67% of the studies reported the sampling of volumes >1m³. For pump sampling the share decreased to 17%, while 66% of the studies applied a volume between 10L and 1m³ and 24% between 10L and 1L. Similar to seawater, for bucket/grab sampling, sampling volumes did not exceed 1 m³ and only in 39% of the studies reached a range between 1 m³ and 10 L, while 58% reported volumes between 10L. Likewise, this is also directly reflected in the applied unit for reporting. While net sampling and pump sampling report items/m³ as major unit, this is replaced by items/L for bucket/grab sampling. Only for net sampling area-based units were reported, with mainly items/km² (22%) in a high share. Like for sea water net sampling studies reported a high share of other units and multiple units per publication. Among all studies, shapes and colours were reported in 88% and 43% of the cases, respectively. All results are summarised in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Overview of reporting of sample collection, lowest size limit, sample preparation, analytical detection, sample volumes, units, shapes and colours, displayed for net, pump and bucket/grab sampling of terrestrial water.

3.1.8. RAP for microplastic analysis in water: **Wastewater**

Sample collection

In the case of wastewaters investigated for microplastics, the sampling was mainly performed using bucket/grab (48%) and pumps (24%) as sampling devices. Yet, a rather high share of “other” sampling devices (17%) was reported, this was higher than both seawater (3%) and terrestrial water (3%). These other devices consisted mainly of two systems, gravity-based filtration systems and 24 h composite autosamplers. The pump and bucket/grab sampling techniques mainly aimed for lowest size detection limits <0.1 mm (67% and 66%, respectively).

For both methods, sample splitting was indicated by the collected data. Remarkably, compared to the other water bodies, it was applied three times more often for pump sampling in wastewater analyses.

Sample preparation

The numbers of separations steps increased compared to the two other compartments. Compared to terrestrial waters, the number of steps increased strongly to where a high share of >=5 numbers of steps (26 % each) was achieved. For pump sampling this was also the maximum share while a second peak was found for two processing steps (21%). For bucket/grab sampling a maximum was found for three steps (30%). Interestingly for pump sampling, the relatively high share (7%) of non-treated samples for analysis was found.

Both findings are also reflected in the type of digestion and separation steps reported. While filtration is applied in the most cases, visual separation only had a share of 33% for pump sampling. In 47% of the cases an oxidative digestion and/or a density separation was applied. Interestingly, the share of “other” and enzymatic digestion reached a minimum share of 10% for pump sampling of wastewaters. Bucket/grab sampling had even a higher share of oxidative digestion steps (72%) as well as sieving. Coincidentally, this was also the highest for all compartments while visual separation was reported in a similar share. Further details are presented in the combined section on sample preparation (Section 3.1.10).

Analytical detection and plastic quantification

Identification techniques used with wastewater samples were mainly performed using optical microscopy (61% - 76%) and FTIR based analyses (47 – 64%). The application of Raman spectroscopy

(~26%) increased compared to seawater and terrestrial water, while SEM analysis (2% to 7%) was applied at a very low rate. Also, thermoanalytical (14 %, pump sampling) approaches and fluorescent staining (3% - 12.5%) approaches were reported at notable rates. Further details are presented in the combined section on analytical detection (Section 3.1.11).

Data reporting

The differences in sample volume were less pronounced for wastewater than it was for seawater and terrestrial water. For pump sampling 19% of the studies reported sample volumes >1 m³, while 64% of the studies applied a volume between 10L and 1m³ and 22% between 10L and 1L which is highly similar to terrestrial waters. For bucket/grab sampling, volumes did not exceed 1 m³ and 45% of the studies reached a range between 1 m³ and 10 L, while 52% reported volumes lower 10L. This is also directly reflected in the applied unit for reporting. In both cases items/L have the highest percentage (pump 56% and bucket/grab 79%) and items/m³ is only reported with 7% for bucket/grab sampling, while it was reported with 33% for pump sampling. Further, for pump sampling often multiple units were reported within a study, so the overall percentage exceeds 100%. Among all studies, shapes and colours were reported in 84% and 49% of the cases, respectively. All results are summarised in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Overview of sample collection, lowest size limit, sample preparation, analytical detection, reporting of sample volumes, units, shapes and colours, displayed for net, pump and bucket/grab sampling of wastewater.

3.1.9. Nanoplastic analysis for water samples

It was not possible to create RAPs for nanoplastics. The investigated studies focused on surface waters (sea water and terrestrial compartments), snow and one on wastewaters. Sampling was performed by grab sampling, scoops/shovel (snow), cores (snow) and composite sampling. Sample volumes are mainly below 1L and always below 1 m³.

Sample preparation is highly variable, often designed towards the analytical technique but in most cases have a filtration step either direct, after a chemical digestion (oxidative, acid, or alkaline) or density separation. The SR found that NaCl was the most commonly used salt.

As analytical tools various instruments covering SEM, μRaman, dye staining, pyr-GC-MS and other techniques based on mass spectrometry, particle tracking analysis or dynamic light scattering were reported.

3.1.10. Sample preparation for plastics in water samples: all subcompartments

Even though various sample collection methods are used and water bodies investigated, the sample preparation steps tend to follow a similar trend. In total, five major steps are visible for the extraction of microplastics: **filtration**, **visual separation**, **oxidative digestion**, **density separation**, and **sieving** across all investigated size classes (see Figure 5). All later shown percentage ranges give the maximum and minimum applications shares found for the three sampling strategies.

Figure 5 – Heatmap of applied sample preparation steps used in the analysis of microplastics in water samples.

Filtration and sieving

Various types of filters have been applied for sample preparation when working with microplastics. Among the reported filters, four types were mainly applied, stainless steel, cellulose, synthetic and glass fibre filters. Especially for bucket/grab sampling a high percentage of synthetic filters was reported, while pump and net sampling showed a major use of glass fibre filters. These synthetic filters may pose a risk for sample contamination. Stainless steel filters were applied with a share of 13 to 25% within the investigated studies. Interestingly, for sieving was almost always performed using stainless-steel filters. An overlap between both processes (filtration and sieving) cannot be excluded. However, sieving is often applied using a larger apparatus like metal sieves in the form of sieving stacks while the filtration requires normally a filter funnel and is supported by the application of vacuum. Still, rather often the type of sieve and/or filter was not properly reported.

Visual separation

Visual separation is used for the analysis of microplastics, many of the times it was reported often without any further details, or was stated as “not applicable” (44% to 58%). In 20% to 33 % of the cases “other” was marked and the applied identification guidelines remarked. Visual separation has the advantage that it can be linked to sample splitting (Löder et al. 2017, Primpke et al. 2020) which allows the introduction of a filtration step as a dedicated sample preparation for larger microplastics using visual identification guidelines and smaller microplastics by more complex techniques. Within the dataset a series of studies perform this approach (e.g., Frias et al. 2020, Mintenig et al. 2020).

Oxidative digestion

Oxidative digestion is mainly performed using H₂O₂ (62% to 71%) and Fenton's reagent (22% to 34%), which applies Fe(SO₄) as catalyst in combination with H₂O₂ to significantly reduce the reaction time. Both cases combined reached 93% to 99% application rates for the three sampling strategies, so application of at least H₂O₂ is the method of choice. Additionally, the use of this peroxide is already well investigated and preserves all important polymer types (Lusher et al. 2020). Further, if applied using Fenton's reagent, the reaction time can be reduced from several hours down 30 minutes in many cases (Al-Azzawi et al. 2020). Still, in contrast to early applications which had used the NOAA protocol, high temperature should be avoided due to the different thermally driven reaction pathways. In the presence of the Fe²⁺ catalyst, the reaction is strongly exothermic (Al-Azzawi et al. 2020). Therefore, in recent years the temperature of the reaction is monitored and often the mixture cooled with e.g., an ice bath. Further, the brand and quality of the H₂O₂ may influence the performance of the reaction (Al-Azzawi et al. 2020). In the case of high organic matter content, the reaction can be applied multiple times to avoid large volumes (Cunsolo et al. 2021).

Density separation

The application of density separation in microplastic analysis aims to remove inorganic materials with higher densities, for example sand or sediment grains or residuals from diatom shells. Density separation on water samples is mainly performed using NaCl (27% to 66%) and to a far lower percentage by ZnCl₂ (9% to 50%) and NaI (7% to 10%). Other salts or oils were applied in few cases. For net sampling, many entries (22 %) were assigned to "other". Here, the seawater itself was used for density separation to extract the floating microplastics, which is also reflected in the reported densities.

Overall, two trends became visible in water sample preparation with (a) the application of NaCl, which is comparably cheap and easy to handle, and (b) denser solutions, which often need more expensive salts and may have environmental hazards as reported for ZnCl₂ (Ivleva et al. 2017). Still, the density has a major influence on the analysis of microplastics, as polymers with a higher density might be missed or reported underrepresented (Ivleva et al. 2017). While not applied for water samples, with NaBr an additional salt solution is available in the reported density range, which has a lower cost compared to NaI and ZnCl₂.

3.1.11. Analytical detection and identification techniques for microplastics in water samples

For this section, all water sample types were treated together because similar identification techniques were applied. Many studies applied more than one technique for the identification of microplastics. This is presented in Figure 6 using a cross table. There were only two cases where a single technique was applied within a study, these were QCL-IR and TED-GC-MS based analyses. As for the other approaches, visual identification techniques (visual determination and optical microscopy) were often linked to other chemical analysis techniques like FTIR and Raman spectroscopy. The exact type of performance of these techniques was linked to the reported lower size limit.

Figure 6 – Cross table showing the applied chemical identification techniques.

While unaided visual identification was mainly performed when high size detection limits were reported, it was also often linked to FTIR based analyses (ATR-FTIR and unspecified instruments). Optical microscopy was one of the most applied methods across all size detection limits. With the decreasing size detection limit, the application rate of ATR-FTIR and unspecified FTIR was reduced, while the rates for μ FTIR, (μ)Raman and fluorometric approaches increased. SEM was applied especially for small sized particles. This technique was mainly used to characterize surface changes in details, sometimes combined with EDX to determine the element composition of the particles.

The application of optical microscopy was reported 19% of the studies as the only identification tool. In 81% of the studies, it was supported by the different types of chemical identification, mainly FTIR (57%), Raman (18%) and fluorescent staining (4%). Among the other applied techniques (19%) it was supported by a hot needle or melt point test to determine the synthetic origin of the selected particles. In many cases a series of analytical tools was applied on the particles depending on the research question. As analytical filters are commonly designed and validated for the spectroscopic approaches as well as the instruments, their use was not part of the current analyses.

Chemical analysis was often performed partially and needs a designated sampling strategy. Several pathways are available here (Brandt et al. 2021, Mintenig et al. 2020, Schymanski et al. 2021) which depend on the investigated size, analytical approach and filter type. For many types of analyses, automated or even automatic approaches are available (Primpke et al. 2020) and their existence is considered for the SWOT analysis (see Primpke et al. 2023, *manuscript in preparation*). Lastly, information on costs and personnel demands is available in the study of Primpke et al. (2020).

3.1.12. Quality control measures and data reporting

In terms of quality control, 53% percent of the studies applied any type procedural blank correction and even a smaller number (27%) reported the performance of air blanks. Further, only 16% of the reference reported on a positive control or recovery test. Procedural blanks were still more common for bucket/grab and pump sampling compared to net sampling which is highly linked to the high number of publications between 2018 and 2020, which reflects the higher awareness of their necessity. A rather upcoming technique is the performance of steps or the whole analysis using clean rooms or laminar-flow cabinets. Such measures were reported in 16% of the studies, and more commonly used for pump sampling-based analyses. The raw data was only reported in 33% of the investigated studies for microplastics.

3.2. SWOT analysis for plastics in water samples

The SWOT analysis is not part of this report and will be provided in a following publication (see Primpke et al. 2023, *manuscript in preparation*).

4. Discussion

For macroplastics, two sampling strategies already reach rather high TRL levels (see Figure 7). In contrast to litter in solid compartments the available techniques did not yet reach a consensus for monitoring of these plastics. Still, many studies link to the existing guidelines and use parts of them for investigations.

	TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
Basic research	1							
	2							
	3							
Applied research	4	Terrestrial water						
	5							
Development	6		Net sampling					
	7	Sea water	Visual surveys		Object identification	Object identification		Protocols
Implementation	8							
	9							

Figure 7 – Technical Readiness Level (TRL) Map for the analysis of Macroplastics.

Two major pathways of sampling strategies were derived. It was found that the sampling technique had a major influence on the lower size detection limit while this limit can also be set during the sample preparation. By the combined investigation of sample preparation steps and analytical tools, it became clear, that particles with as size larger 0.3 mm follow a different analytical pathway compared to smaller-sized particles.

Therefore, the results indicate the use of net sampling for particles larger 0.3 mm in size followed by an optional organic matter digestion, depending on the level of organic material, as well as an optional density separation followed by visual separation and identification linked to a plastic identity analysis on at least a subsample of the particles. This analytical pathway already reached a TRL of 8 and was very often applied (see Figure 8).

	TRL	Survey design	Sample collection	Sample preparation	Analytical detection	Plastic quantification	QA/QC	Data reporting
Basic research	1							
	2							
	3							
Applied research	4			Acid digestion	NIR imaging			
	5		Composite sampling		Thermoanalytical (TED GC-MS, PY-GC-MS) Unaided visual/Object identification		Field blanks Positive controls	International databases
Development	6	Sea water Terrestrial water Wastewater			Fluorometric techniques		Air blanks	
	7			Alkaline digestion Enzymatic digestion	SEM-(EDX) Hot needle/melt point assessment		Air filtrations systems	Raw data in publications
Implementation	8		Net sampling Pump sampling Bucket/Grab sampling		Chemical ID with RAMAN (including microscopy)	items/km ²	Procedure blanks	
	9			Oxidative Digestion, Filtration/sieving, Visual Separation, Density separation	Optical microscopy Chemical ID with FTIR (ATR, general and microscopy)	items/m ³ items/L		

Figure 8 – Technical Readiness Level (TRL) Map for the analysis of Microplastics.

The analysis of smaller sized (<0.3 mm) particles are optimally sampled either using pump or bucket&/grab sampling followed by a filtration/sieving step. In this size range the digestion of organic matter digestion was performed in almost 2/3 of the publications and can therefore be considered mandatory followed by an optional density separation depending on the investigated water source. Analysis should include a plastic identity analysis on at least a subsample of the particles collected. In the context of the investigated literature, this analytical pathway already reached a TRL of 8 and was very often applied (see Figure 8).

Still, an optimal selection of the sampling device covering all size classes was not possible, as each of the systems covered different sample volumes ranging for several m³ of water for nets towards a few litres for bucket/grab sampling. In the scope of SR an evaluation of the optimal instrument for monitoring was impossible as most studies were performed as research projects and did not cover systematic elements necessary for monitoring.

5. Conclusion

Existing monitoring methods dedicated to the quantification of nano-, micro-, and macroplastics in water have been identified, based on a systematic literature review (SR). From a large set of 3290 papers have been published in scientific peer review literature that were matching one or more of the selected keywords of our SR. We removed reviews and obviously non relevant papers through a process of title screening and pairwise title and abstract reading. Finally full literature reading and data extraction focused on 1859 papers of which over 750 included analysis of water compartments.

The major conclusions deduced from the SR process were:

1. Many publications focused on the OSPAR region and the Mediterranean. Within Europe, research studies on plastics are not equally distributed. e.g., for the matrix biota, no publications were identified in the Black Sea.
2. An impressive number of papers addressed methodological aspects but in many instances the description of methods provided by authors was insufficient to understand and reconstruct the methodology they used. They did not reach an acceptable scientific level when relevant

information about methods, sampling positions and reagents were missing. This is a big problem for scientific quality, to replicate the experiments, and to compare data among different papers.

3. Much of the recent literature does not follow the latest methodological recommendations. People tend to apply methods already applied in other research campaigns, and only in few instances did they push method development. Similarly, studies which applied routine monitoring approaches tended to use older techniques with little technological improvement. Applying updated methods to already running sampling campaigns could be sometimes regarded as impossible as doing so would mess up long-term data. If reference to the difference between the improved methods is not provided, people will continue using the old methods to have comparable data.
4. Only a small part of the publications identified through the SR make their full dataset publicly available within the supportive information or within Open Access data repositories.
5. There are size barriers in analysis and no universal method is applicable for all sizes. Different sizes lead to different monitoring methods and different suggestions for standard approaches.
6. The number of papers on plastics research has strongly increased over the last years, in particular for solids, this has led to a high and increasing number of methods, resulting in high heterogeneity in RAPs.
7. Publications on nanoplastics are still limited.
8. The QA/QC is weakly described in many papers. For example, in for microplastic research, reporting on the applied filtration system is often poor or positive control samples are not applied. Whereas this could be expected for older literature (>5 years), more recent publications should meet minimum requirements (see e.g. Cowger et. al. 2020).
9. Too many papers are lacking detailed information on contamination and no information is provided to assess if background contamination originates from the environment or just fieldwork, procedural or lab contamination.
10. Many papers do not report the lower size limit of particles that can be detected by the method.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. Monitoring studies on plastics in water compartments should be separated into particles larger 300 μm and smaller 300 μm based on the targeted particle sizes.
2. There is a requirement for better quality control by systematically introducing procedural blanks, air blanks and positive controls when smaller plastic fragments are analysed. Development of a set of minimum QA/QC requirements and guidelines on how to apply these is recommended.
3. The lower size limit is an important characteristic of each method, essential for data comparability. It should always be reported. It can depend on the shape of the particle (fibre versus particle).
4. It is necessary to study how data from different continents can be harmonised or compared.
5. Because methods for nanoplastics determination in water samples are currently not developed enough, more research is needed before implementation in monitoring programs.

6. Monitoring guidelines should provide data handling information, including the reporting of processed data (e.g. reporting of mean or median, using arithmetic or logarithmic mean), including details in methods description.

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